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How and why does demographic decline lead to support for populist parties? The case of the Czech Republic

Tomáš Dvořák^{a,*}, Jan Zouhar^b, Jan Bíba^c

^a Institute of Sociological Studies, Faculty of Social Sciences, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic

^b Department of Econometrics, Faculty of Informatics and Statistics, Prague University of Economics and Business, Prague, Czech Republic

^c Department of Political Science, Faculty of Arts, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic

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ABSTRACT

In recent decades, a strong demographic decline has characterized post-communist Central and Eastern European countries. Using the Czech Republic as a case study, we apply a multilevel structural equation model to test the mechanism whereby demographic decline translates into support for populist parties. Combining regional and individual data, we show that the long-term demographic decline (measured at the regional level) recorded between 2008 and 2017 had an impact on preferences in favour of two populist parties: the radical populist party, Freedom and Direct Democracy (SPD), and a more moderate populist party, ANO 2011. The results of this analysis point to a mechanism where demographic decline is associated with a breakdown of social capital, which is then associated with voting behaviour in favour of both populist parties.

1. Introduction

In recent decades, research on populism has often focused on the sources of populist party support. This research has considered both individual factors and contextual sources. Individual sources are measured at the individual level. These may be, for example, income levels, values or attitudes. Contextual factors, on the other hand, represent the influence of the environment in which people live. Although research has focused largely on the former (e.g., Rooduijn, 2018; Santana, Zagórski, & Rama, 2020), the latter has also been frequently examined in recent years (Evans & Ivaldi, 2020; Savelkoul, Laméris, & Tolsma, 2017; Van Wijk, Bolt, & Johnston, 2019).

This article focuses on the contextual sources of populist party support in Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries. The purpose of the empirical analysis is inspired by Ivan Krastev (Krastev & Holmes, 2019), who linked the rise of populism in CEE countries with demographic decline. The idea that the context of population decline (decreasing natural increase, ageing populations, outmigration, etc.) may work as a source of populism has been recently explored in Western European countries with mixed results (Harteveld, Van Der Brug, De Lange, & Van Der Meer, 2022; van Leeuwen, Halleck Vega, & Hogenboom, 2021). Nonetheless, the countries of the CEE region represent a particularly suitable case for exploring these effects. Over the past three

decades, post-communist countries of this region have witnessed significant population decline, with some countries losing a substantial part of their population (Lang, Henn, Wladimir, & Ehrlich, 2015).

This paper wants to draw attention to demographic decline as a source of populism and support for populist parties in particular. We argue that demographic decline may impact the respective communities by eroding community cohesion and social capital—it becomes difficult to maintain existing social connections and ties. As a result, social interconnectedness between people in a given community declines. A decline in social capital is manifested by deteriorating social networks and low social trust. These may lead to support for nativist (and illiberal) populist parties since low social capital and social trust have been found to be associated with negative views towards outgroups, as well as exclusionary attitudes.

This new mechanism is tested while controlling for other factors, in particular, the economic situation of a region. Demographic decline usually brings with it major economic problems. And since the impact of an unfavourable economic context has previously been examined (e.g., Sipma & Lubbers, 2020), in this study, we focus mainly on other mechanisms beyond economic problems (i.e., social capital); nonetheless, we also control for economic factors.

The paper thus aims to investigate the association between demographic decline and support for populist parties, with a focus on how

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: tomas.dvorak@fsv.cuni.cz (T. Dvořák), zouharj@vse.cz (J. Zouhar), jan.biba@ff.cuni.cz (J. Bíba).

this relationship is mediated. *Thus, the research question asks in what way a (district-level) environment characterized by demographic decline influences the susceptibility of people towards populist sentiments and a vote for populist parties. In other words, what links the context, characterized here by demographic decline, and an individual's support for a populist party?*

This analysis focuses on the Czech Republic, a country in Central and Eastern Europe (CEE). The region has experienced democratization since the 1990s involving significant social and economic change. These changes have led to economic transformation and deindustrialization, but also demographic shifts. One example is East Germany, which witnessed a significant shift of people from east to west after 1989 and the German reunification (Weisskircher, 2020). Similarly, in other countries, there has been an outflow (especially of young people) to Western European countries (Krastev & Holmes, 2019). However, it was not just overall outmigration taking pace but also intra-regional population shifts within countries. Consequently, regional polarization within these countries began to occur. These were processes that had multiple causes, including the aforementioned deindustrialization but also, for example, the growth of new industrial centres, usually in urban regions (Rehák, Rafaj, & Černěnko, 2021).¹ This thus raises the question of how this sharp inter-regional polarization will affect political attitudes and preferences.

Virtually the entire CEE region is facing significant demographic changes (Dijkstra, 2017). In this article, we focus on only one aspect of demographic decline: regional polarization within a country. The analysis presented here tests this mechanism in the Czech Republic, one of many CEE countries where these changes are present, albeit there are cases where regional polarization has been even more drastic (Daugirdas & Pociute-Sereikiene, 2018; Weisskircher, 2020). The Czech Republic therefore presents a reasonable and representative case study of the influence of demographic decline in the form of inter-regional polarization on the choice of a populist political party.

2. Contextual sources of populist vote choices

Over the past two decades, research focusing on sources of populist party choice in Western Europe (WE) as well as in CEE countries has focused on both individual and contextual sources.

To date, the empirical research focusing on individual-level factors has focused mostly on populist radical right parties (PRRPs) in WE countries. Objective variables such as economic hardship (unemployment, low income) have been considered; subjective (attitudinal) variables have included feelings of being left behind, distrust of political institutions, social trust, Euroscepticism and attitudes towards immigration. In general, research on PRRPs has shown the importance of these factors, with the caveat that it always depends on the specific country and context (Backlund & Jungar, 2019; e.g. Rooduijn, 2018; Van Hauwaert & Van Kessel, 2018).

Research on the sources of populist party choice in the post-communist CEE region is complicated because, in addition to PRRPs, non-radical (centrist) populism is also present (Havlík & Voda, 2018; Stanley, 2017). First, regarding radical (nativist) populist parties in CEE, the sources of choice for these parties are not significantly different from those of the WE region. Santana et al. (2020) show that Euroscepticism is the strongest predictor of the choice for these parties across countries in the CEE region. A significant effect of attitudes towards immigration has been demonstrated as well. However, other factors often mentioned as important in the WE context, such as economic hardship and unemployment, do not seem to have as strong an influence as radical parties in WE (Santana et al., 2020). Second, in the case of centrist populism in CEE, broader comparative empirical analyses are rather lacking, mainly

because the exact classification of these parties is difficult. Moreover, the existing analyses do not suggest a single and clear source of choice for these centrist populist parties (Havlík & Voda, 2018). The emerging picture seems to be that these centrist populist parties exploit emerging cleavages unaccounted for by existing mainstream political parties (Haughton & Deegan-Krause, 2020; Saxonberg & Heinisch, 2022).

However, individual factors may not be the only ones influencing the support for and choice of these parties. Therefore, analyses, particularly in WE countries, have also focused on contextual factors. By “contextual factors”, we mean the effect of the residential (environment) context over and above individual variables.

In WE countries, this discussion about how context impacts support for populist parties has revolved mainly around two contextual factors: (a) unemployment and (b) the proportion of foreigners/immigrants/ethnic minorities in a given region or locality.

The thesis that contextual unemployment (i.e., the level of unemployment in a region/district) will influence voting behaviour follows from the assumption that the choice of populist parties is influenced by negative objective and macrostructural processes (i.e., grievances) (Rydgren, 2007). These (macro) processes then influence attitudes and values (negative attitudes towards immigration, feelings of having been left behind, feelings of relative deprivation, etc.) that lead to the choice of respective populist parties (Spruyt, Keppens, & Van Droogenbroeck, 2016). For example, living in economically lagging regions may induce feelings of relative deprivation or negative attitudes towards outgroups, which in turn leads to support and voting choices in favour of PRRPs (Gidron & Hall, 2017; Salomo, 2019). However, in the case of contextual unemployment, the empirical evidence is present but not very strong. A meta-study of the effect of contextual unemployment on the choice of radical populist parties in different countries showed only a small effect on voting behaviour (Sipma & Lubbers, 2020).

Concerning the presence of foreigners/immigrants/ethnic minorities, the current knowledge is a little clearer. Respective analyses have typically been framed by ethnic threat theory (Van Wijk et al., 2019), which predicts that the presence of ethnic minorities will be associated with feelings of threat and, subsequently, the choice of a populist party (usually PRRPs). First, this hypothesis was based on the mere presence of ethnic minorities in a given region or district; some studies have confirmed this hypothesis (Savelkoul et al., 2017), whereas others have not (de Blok, Lisanne, & van der Meer, 2018). Recently, however, a new thesis has emerged suggesting that it is not necessarily the mere presence of ethnic groups but rather a “halo effect”: the presence of ethnic minorities not in a given district but at a sufficient distance. This “distant” presence can foster feelings of danger and threat. Thus, the strong presence of an ethnic minority near (but not within) a homogeneous native population strongly increases the probability of choosing PRRPs. Recent research strongly supports this hypothesis (Evans & Ivaldi, 2020; Rydgren & Ruth, 2013; van Wijk, Bolt, & Tolsma, 2020).

Finally, it was recently proposed that populist party choice is also driven by demographic factors. Demographic decline not only leads to economic problems, such as rising unemployment and an overall decline in living standards, but it also indicates deteriorating infrastructure, deteriorating quality of public services, and even declining social and cultural capital. Thus, it was unsurprisingly hypothesized that demographic decline and related processes can lead to populist attitudes and anti-establishment sentiments. In WE countries, the empirical research has provided mixed evidence so far (Harteveld, Van Der Brug, De Lange, & Van Der Meer, 2022; van Leeuwen et al., 2021). Over the past few decades, while WE countries have not been strongly affected by demographic decline, the CEE region has experienced significant demographic decline (Lang et al., 2015). This makes the CEE region a good case for testing the presented hypotheses.

This paper thus engages in a debate about the contextual sources of support for populist parties with two objectives: The first is to demonstrate the effect of demographic decline on support for populist parties. The second (key) objective is to analyse mediation: How does

¹ The argument here is that the EU cohesion policy emphasis on investment in specific regions (with universities, in urban regions, with growth potential, etc.) increases inter-regional disparities.

demographic decline impact people's attitudes so that they support populist parties? Thus, we are concerned with describing the pathway whereby demographic decline leads to support for populist parties. This problem is particularly relevant for the countries of the CEE region, where, over the last decade, the level of populism and the rise of illiberal politics has been extremely strong (Hanley & Vachudova, 2018).

3. Demographic decline as a source of support for populist parties

Over the past three decades, many CEE countries have experienced demographic decline, which included processes of population ageing, declining natural increase (sometimes resulting in natural decrease) and outmigration. These processes have been extremely strong in countries and regions such as eastern Germany, the Baltic states, Bulgaria and Romania, and they have led to strong regional polarization. They have also been present in other CEE countries, while not necessarily as drastic (Dijkstra, 2017; Lang et al., 2015).

Why do demographic changes affect electoral behaviour? Demographic decline has major long-term economic and social consequences (Hospers & Reverda, 2015). It can be associated with de-industrialization and the associated outflow of labour (young, skilled, educated, etc.), resulting in economic underdevelopment, rising unemployment, reduced investments and so on (Bartholomae, Woon Nam, & Schoenberg, 2017). Relatedly, demographic decline can also impact living standards, for example, with lower municipal budgets, lower investment in infrastructure, lower service quality and fewer schools (van Leeuwen et al., 2021). Another effect is on the local community and its cohesion—depopulation can set in motion the disintegration of social life in some cases. However, even weaker forms of demographic decline can lead to a breakdown of social ties and social capital (Bell, 2009). Thus, rather than having a single effect, demographic decline is a multidimensional process.

A multitude of mechanisms can thus affect political attitudes, anti-establishment and populist sentiments and, hence, support for populist parties. The following specific mechanisms in the literature link demographic change to support for populist parties.

Ivan Krastev focuses directly on the situation in post-communist CEE countries and the population decline in the region (Krastev & Holmes, 2019). He argues that these states have systematically lost their young and educated populations in recent decades, leading to (often unspoken) fears that may not be directly manifested but revealed in situations of subjective threat, such as the migration crisis. Ivan Krastev introduces the concept of demographic panic: people who feel anxious and threatened by the extinction of their own population take strong anti-immigration positions and lean towards populism. However, it is an idea that has been proposed on a theoretical level without empirical evidence and without providing guidance on how to measure this hypothesis empirically.

Rafaela Dancygier et al. mention demographic changes in the context of Germany when they argue that the arrival of (male) refugees in Germany has changed the ratio of men and women and mate competition. According to the analysis (Dancygier, Egami, Jamal, & Rischke, 2021), this has led—also supported by the discourse of far-right populist parties—to an increase in hate crimes against refugees. Similarly, Salomo (2019) describes developments in eastern Germany that have been characterized by increasing demographic homogeneity in terms of an ageing population, skewed adult sex ratios, the outmigration of mainly young and educated females and so on. These demographic developments are then associated with increased dissatisfaction with democracy and ethnocentric attitudes. These demographic changes are thus associated with a shift towards more radical positions.

Demographic change is also analysed by Hartevelde, Van Der Brug, De Lange, & Van Der Meer (2022), who show that the proportion of young people living in a region (and thus a proxy for demographic ageing) is associated with populist attitudes and, consequently, with support for

the Dutch populist party, the Party for Freedom (PVV). The authors of this study argue that demographic decline is also associated with local marginalization and less access to services and is specifically true in rural and non-urban (semi-urban) areas (Hartevelde, Van Der Brug, De Lange, & Van Der Meer, 2022).²

The impact of local marginalization, measured by access to public services, should stem from the fact that reduced natural increase or outmigration leads in most countries to lower public budget contributions. This decreased funding can make it difficult to maintain existing service quality, potentially leading to increased political discontent and, accordingly, support for populist parties. However, these results have been confirmed in some countries, but not in others (Hartevelde, Van Der Brug, De Lange, & Van Der Meer, 2022; Salomo, 2019). The results are therefore inconclusive so far.

These studies show that demographic decline is associated in various ways with preferences that lead to support for populism or populist parties. The variables used in these analyses (e.g., immigration attitudes, availability of services, evaluation of the economic situation) will also be used as control variables in our analysis.

3.1. Demographic decline and social capital

In this paper, we argue that demographic decline in a given locality can also have a negative impact on social capital, which Robert D. Putnam defines as the interconnectedness of people in social networks and the resulting mutual trust in other people—members of the community (Putnam, 2000).

Population decline can weaken social networks or even dissolve them, making it difficult to maintain a sense of community. Social trust is gradually eroded when norms of reciprocity decline, cooperation within the community diminishes, involvement in community affairs drops, interactions become scarcer and cooperation leading to the establishment of neighbourhood norms becomes more and more difficult (Bridger & Alter, 2006, p. 13). People remaining in shrinking regions are usually of lower status and higher age, and severe population loss can lead to total social disintegration and the collapse of entire communities (Rocak, Hospers, & Reverda, 2016). But even a gradual decline in formal and informal connections progressively leads to increased isolation and increased difficulties in accessing social capital. An ageing population also generally entails a lower capacity to take initiative and lower activity in civic and social life, with the capacity of people to get involved in common projects decreasing (Do Carmo, 2010; Martinez-Fernandez, Audirac, Fol, & Cunningham-Sabot, 2012). Demographic decline can thus lead to communities becoming less connected and to mutual trust and norms of reciprocity being weakened (Bell, 2009).

Low levels of social capital can also be related to support for populist parties and PRRPs in particular (Berning & Ziller, 2017). The effect of social trust, which Putnam saw as a manifestation of functioning social networks and which has been used as a direct measure of social capital, has been frequently studied. Studies examining the effect of low social trust on the choice of populist parties posit that it is indicative of social isolation, which is associated with negative evaluations of outgroups and exclusionary attitudes. This stems from a perception of the world as a dangerous place, and a rich body of research confirms that this outlook is associated with intolerance, distrust and a negative evaluation of outgroups (Sipinen, Söderlund, & Bäck, 2020; Thomsen & Rafiqi, 2020). By contrast, higher levels of social trust, which result from stronger social engagement and networks, promote tolerance, cooperation and acceptance of outgroups (Herreros & Criado, 2009; Radkiewicz, Skarzyoska, & Hamer, 2013). Since exclusionary attitudes are an essential

² The authors of this study combine both the proportion of young people and the availability of services (in a given district) into one indicator, which makes it difficult to interpret the results.

element of the PRRPs' populism, the effect on support for this type of party is to be expected (Hameleers & de Vreese, 2020).

The effect of low social trust on the increased likelihood of voting for populist parties has been demonstrated in the context of WE (Berning & Ziller, 2017). In several CEE countries, Jens Rydgren found the effect of social capital on higher probabilities of voting for populist parties to be relatively weak. However, the results also suggest that low-trusting people were non-voting at the time; they preferred the "exit" option (i. e., abstaining from the electoral process by not voting for any political party) (Rydgren, 2011). On top of that, the respective analyses were performed on data from the period (2006/2007) preceding the sharp rise in populist sentiment in most countries in the CEE region. For example, the rise of populist sentiments in the Czech Republic occurred only after 2010. Thus, with the rise of supply-side populism, non-voting (exit) might conceivably translate into voting behaviour (voice) much more strongly.

We thus hypothesize that demographic decline is associated with low levels of social capital, which in turn leads to increased support for populist parties.

In our analysis, we controlled for the effect of economic hardship. As exemplified by eastern Germany and the Baltic states, extreme cases of demographic decline, for example, in the form of shrinking cities and regions, can have far-reaching economic consequences (Bartholomae et al., 2017). Population size (number of inhabitants) is often linked to government financial contributions, and therefore population decline can lead to a deterioration in service levels, infrastructure and so on. Significantly, demographic decline leads to a downturn in the local economy, constrained investment and a deterioration in the quality of the labour force. Additionally, the costs of an ageing population remaining in the region increase, putting a strain, among other things, on public budgets. Overall, population decline leads to a deterioration in living standards and quality of life, and it is usually a source of deepening economic problems (McCann, 2017).

When the influence of contextual economic factors on the choice of populist parties is examined, contextual unemployment is the variable most commonly considered when measuring economic hardship (de Blok et al., 2018; Sipma & Lubbers, 2020). The argument is that populist actors opportunistically use high unemployment levels to justify blaming the central government, offering simplistic solutions and inciting populist sentiments (Bermeo & Bartels, 2014). Thus, when measuring the effect of context, we also included contextual levels of unemployment as a control variable to take into account the impact of the economic decline.

Finally, we also included a contextual variable measuring the presence of foreigners (from outside of the EU) in the given district. We incorporated this as a control variable but also for the sake of completion, given the current state of empirical research (see Section 2). The proportion of foreigners could be associated with anti-immigrant attitudes, which also work as an important source of voting in favour of populist parties.

Overall, our hypothesis can be seen as an elaboration of the general thesis that populism (in the form of attitudes and voting behaviour) is a manifestation and consequence of macro-structural processes (Rydgren, 2007). It is in this context that the influence of globalization and the so-called "losers of globalization" hypothesis is most often discussed, with an emphasis on economic change and the resulting economic grievances. These ideas have also been applied in the context of the evolution of regional polarization, increasing disparities between affluent cities and regions lagging behind—the revenge of "places that do not matter" (Rodríguez-Pose, 2018). Our analysis thus follows this train of thought. However, we are concerned with the impact of demographic change.

4. Context: populist parties in the Czech Republic

This paper focuses on two Czech populist parties: Dawn of Direct

Democracy (Úsvit)/Freedom and Direct Democracy (SPD) and ANO 2011. These two parties represent two main forms of Central and Eastern European populism: respectively, radical nativist and moderate or "centrist" (Stanley, 2017). The labelling of this second type of "centrist" populism varies. But even this more moderate populism is generally viewed as illiberal and also nativist and anti-immigration although to a lesser extent than radical nativist parties (Hanley & Vachudova, 2018).

The most populist of the major Czech parties, Úsvit was founded by Tomio Okamura in 2013. It was initially considered a populist radical right party, but as Hloušek, Kopeček, and Vodová (2020, p. 131) note, in Western Europe, these parties are typically associated with anti-immigration appeals. This was, at least initially, not the case for Úsvit. Cultural issues, including immigration, were absent from the Czech political discourse; the Czech party system traditionally focused on economic distribution issues, with the cultural and ethnic dimension of conflict being secondary and not part of the main line of political conflict (Haughton & Deegan-Krause, 2015). At that time, Úsvit's programme focused on corruption, direct democracy, the criminal culpability of politicians and law and order (Wondreys, 2020). In the 2013 Parliamentary elections, Úsvit received 6.9% of the popular vote and made a successful electoral breakthrough into the Czech party system.

After the start of the migration crisis in 2014, Okamura adopted a strong anti-immigration discourse. This was met with some resistance in the party, where there was opposition to this shift in discourse. Following conflicts within Úsvit, Okamura founded a new party in 2015, SPD, which combined and interlinked into a single discourse illegal immigration, opposition to Islam and Euroscepticism. SPD mainly emphasized security threats to Czech society caused by immigration from the Middle East and Africa. SPD's programme thus began to strongly resemble that of radical populist parties in Western Europe (Hloušek et al., 2020).

This strategy has also been successful because, ever since 2014, immigration has become one of the most salient issues in Czech society and politics. Immigration and security concerns related to the issue of refugee acceptance have become a key focus of the discourse presented by SPD (Wondreys, 2020). In the 2017 parliamentary elections, the party received 10.6% of the votes, and in the 2021 parliamentary elections, this electoral result was repeated. In both elections, the focus of the party's programme remained the same.

The ANO 2011 political movement originated from the ANO (an abbreviation for "action of dissatisfied citizens") civic association, founded in 2011 by Andrej Babiš, a billionaire of Slovak origin. Whether in the form of a civic association or a political movement, the main themes of ANO have been criticism of corruption and ineffective governance. From this perspective, ANO can be considered an example of centrist (Stanley, 2017) or technocratic populism (Buštková & Guasti, 2019).

In the 2013 general elections, the movement finished second place, winning nearly 19% of the vote, allowing it to enter into a coalition government. The party also won by addressing voter concerns about economic prosperity in the aftermath of the 2008 mortgage crisis (Havlík & Voda, 2018). Throughout the election period, ANO remained part of the coalition. During its first term in government, however, ANO began to undergo a transformation, which simultaneously manifested itself rhetorically and ideologically, as well as demographically within its electorate. On the rhetorical and ideological level, while the movement did not abandon its anti-political criticisms of political partisanship and while it continued to emphasize the role of effective governance, it incorporated a negative stance towards immigration in the context of the refugee crisis, using similar tactics as the ruling populist parties in Poland and Hungary (Hanley & Vachudova, 2018). Subsequently, ANO won the 2017 general elections, receiving almost 30% of the votes. In the 2021 national elections, ANO repeated its success, receiving 27% of the votes.

According to the Global Party Survey 2019, SPD is the most populist party in the Czech Republic, rated as fully populist and radically nativist,

with a score of 9.5 on a 10-point populism scale, the highest among Czech parties (Norris, 2019). ANO ranks second, scoring 8.4 on the same scale. SPD represents a radical form of populism, whereas ANO combines a more moderate version, with anti-corruption rhetoric and criticism of migration policies. Together, SPD and ANO are recognized as the most populist parties on the Czech political scene.

5. Data and methods

5.1. Sample

Our primary data source was an excerpt from the Czech Household Panel Survey (CHPS, 2018),³ an open-access dataset provided by the Institute of Sociology of the Czech Academy of Sciences via the Czech Social Science Data Archive. In particular, we used data from the third wave of CHPS that was collected shortly after the 2017 Czech parliamentary election and contained a question regarding each respondent's voting preference.

We combined the CHPS with data on regional (contextual) characteristics at the district level (*okresy*). In the Czech Republic, there are 76 such districts, plus the capital city of Prague, which is a special kind of district itself. The regional data was sourced from the public database of the Czech Statistical Office (Czech Statistical Office, 2018).

In multilevel analyses, the question is, how large is the unit upon which the contextual effects will manifest? Some analyses in the field work with countries as contextual units (Arzheimer, 2009), with regional-level analyses also common (Van Hauwaert, Schimpf, & Dandoy, 2019). Thus, the aforementioned contextual effects can be identified at the macro-context level. In contrast, in some cases, the micro-context is strongly preferred. This is particularly the case in the presence of ethnic minorities, where the attitudes of the majority ethnicity will be specifically sensitive to the presence of ethnic minorities and small units need to be distinguished (Evans & Ivaldi, 2020).

Our analysis operates at the meso level with medium-sized districts. We expect the effect of demographic variables to manifest itself at this level as the impact of demographic context was demonstrated in previous analyses using a similar unit size (Salomo, 2019). Here, we work under the assumption that there is no a priori given at which level contextual effects will materialize, and we are guided by previous research working with demographic variables.

The choice of these districts as contextual units has certain limitations. Although districts were founded as units of governmental administration, they have lost that function in recent decades (they still perform that function in the judicial and police/policing spheres). Being determined historically, the delineation of the districts does not always reflect the present clustering of the economic networks and commuting patterns. This brings about (i) a certain degree of heterogeneity within the districts and (ii) spillovers between contextual effects if the district data is used to represent the context, adding noise to the analysis and potentially weakening the results. Nevertheless, the choice of a more homogenous definition of the contextual units is problematic due to data availability.

5.2. Variables

The dependent variable outlines the respondents' current *party preference* for parliamentary elections. Primarily, we were interested in whether the respondent would vote for (i) the populist radical right party SPD, (ii) the more moderate ANO or (iii) other (non-populist) parties. The respondents could also indicate they would not vote in a parliamentary election; these responses were coded as missing values in the analyses.

The key explanatory variable at the individual level was *social capital*, while *demographic change* was the key one at the contextual level. Apart from these variables, we also included several controls at both levels, described in detail in the subsections below.

5.2.1. Social capital and its measurement

There is no exclusive definition and operationalization for the concept of social capital. In the following analysis, we took a perspective that conceives social capital as a resource and measures it at the individual level as a composite construct. Thus, it was not measured by a single variable but rather by a collection of relevant indicators (Lillbacka, 2006). Social capital was treated as a resource that is embedded in social relations. The following indicators, based on existing literature (Lillbacka, 2006; Villalonga-Olives & Kawachi, 2015) were used: *social trust*, *social networks*, *political discussion*, *donations/fundraising* and *social participation*. In our statistical analyses, these indicators were employed as measurement variables for *social capital*, with the latter being modelled as a latent variable (see Section 5.3 for details).

Social trust is a widely used indicator of social capital. However, alternative approaches to measuring social trust have been used in existing studies. Some of them emphasize the concept of institutional trust (Engbers, Thompson, & Slaper, 2017). In our analysis, we employed the conventional approach and used a survey question measuring trust in other people. Our *social trust* variable contained responses, measured on an 11-point Likert scale, to the question, "Generally speaking, would you say that most people can be trusted or that one can never be too careful when dealing with people?"

The second indicator of social capital measured the respondents' involvement and integration in *social networks*. Emphasis was put on informal interactions, such as engaging in stable social networks in terms of interactions with other people, community ties, and so on (Engbers et al., 2017). The social networks variable was obtained from the questionnaire item "How frequently do you spend your leisure time meeting with friends or relatives who do not reside with you?" with responses measured on a 6-point scale.

In this context, we also added a variable measuring the intensity for which politics was talked about with friends, a factor that has been found to mediate the effect of (residential) context on political attitudes (Colombo & Dinas, 2023). This variable, denoted *political discussion*, was measured by responses to the question "How often do you discuss politics and events in our country with your friends?" on a 6-point scale.

The third indicator is based on the fact that a variable measuring membership in voluntary associations is often used as a measure of social capital (Putnam, 2000). In this sense, altruism or philanthropic action is further emphasized. These activities are most often measured through volunteering or donations. Therefore, we decided to measure social capital based on a yes/no answer to the question "Have you been involved in any monetary donations or fundraising efforts for civic and political activities during last year?"

These indicators should form a robust measure of social capital. However, some studies also include an indicator of participation in other social and cultural activities in their measures of social capital (Lindström, 2006). These social activities include visits to sports events, theatres, cinemas, art exhibitions and the like and are seen as stemming from social networks and their stability in the given community. Our *social participation* variable was obtained as a mean across four questionnaire items, each using a 6-point scale measuring the frequency of the respondent's participation in a specific type of social activity.

5.2.2. Individual-level control variables

Individual-level control variables included in our analyses were of two types: sociodemographic and attitudinal. The former was comprised of *gender* (in the form of a female indicator), *age* (categorical variable with five levels), *education* (ordinal variable with four levels), *household income* (five levels) and recent *unemployment* experience (a yes/no answer to the question "did you receive any unemployment allowance during

³ Details about the research can be found here: www.promenyceskespolecnosti.cz.

last year?”).

We included several attitudinal control variables: (i) *immigration attitude* (an 11-point-scale measure of agreement with the assertion that “people from other countries who come here to live usually enrich, as opposed to disrupting, the local culture”), (ii) *satisfaction with the economy* (single item, 11-point Likert scale), (iii) respondents’ *left-right position* (self-assessed by the respondent on an 11-point Likert scale, 1 = left), and (iv) *political interest* (“How much are you interested in politics?”, 4-point scale). These control variables were found by earlier research to be associated with a vote in favour of populist parties (Elchardus & Spruyt, 2014; Van Hauwaert & Van Kessel, 2018).

5.2.3. Contextual variables

At the contextual (regional) level, three explanatory variables were included. The key contextual factor was *demographic change*, which was measured by the district’s total change in population over a 10-year period (2008–2017). Negative values of *demographic change* represent a demographic decline, hypothesized to reduce social capital. As a robustness test, we also used an alternative model specification that used *net migration* to/from the respective district as a share of the population over the past 10 years (2008–2017).

We included two control variables at the contextual level: the district’s *unemployment* level and the share of *foreigners from non-EU countries* in the district’s population. Both variables were expressed as a percentage and based on 2017 data.

Finally, as an alternative indicator of economic prosperity, we also constructed the change in the availability of public services as a contextual variable. Our *public services* variable was constructed as the change in the number of services per capita over a 5-year period (2012–2017) in a given district.⁴ The services included (i) the capacity of primary schools and the number of (ii) secondary schools, (iii) hospitals, (iv) general practitioners’ offices and (v) homes for the elderly. The *public services* measure was obtained as follows: First, each of the five types of services was min-max normalized in individual years. Next, we obtained the difference between 2012 and 2017. Finally, we obtained the mean of the difference across all five types of services. The data were obtained from the Czech Statistical Office.

5.3. Estimation strategy

The main goal of our empirical analysis was to correctly quantify the link symbolically described as “demographic context → social capital → support for a populist party”. Our estimation strategy was chosen with three key features of our analysis in mind. Firstly, *social capital* was not observed directly but could be measured through a battery of proxies. Secondly, our data exhibited a hierarchical structure, with individual responses nested within districts, necessitating a model that could appropriately account for the non-independence of observations within each district and allow for unobserved heterogeneity across districts. Finally, party choice was a categorical variable, warranting the use of models suited for multinomial dependent variables. These features led us to employ multilevel structural equation modelling (SEM), which could reflect them all in a single model.

The overall structure of the SEM model is outlined in Fig. 1. Several key elements of the model are worth commenting on. Firstly, as mentioned in Section 5.2.1, *social capital* was modelled as a latent variable, measured by a combination of observed variables. Secondly, to account for the multilevel structure of our data, we used district-level random effects; two different random effects were included, one affecting the propensity of supporting SPD or ANO and another affecting the measurement equations of *social capital*. Thirdly, due to the multinomial nature of our dependent variable (*party preference*), we applied a multinomial logistic functional form in our main structural equation.

Finally, both contextual variables with strictly positive values (*unemployment* and *foreigners from non-EU countries*) exhibited excessive skewness; to avoid a potentially adverse effect on regression estimates, we log-transformed their values before all calculations.

The SEM model tests the effect of contextual variables on *social capital* (individual variable) and, simultaneously, the effect of *social capital* on *party preference*. All this while controlling for both socio-demographic variables (*gender, age, education, household income, unemployment*) and attitudinal variables (*immigration attitude, satisfaction with the economy, left-right position, political interest*).

When establishing the effect of most contextual variables, we apply the principle of time separation: the contextual variables are aggregated over several years (10 years for *demographic change* and *net migration*, 5 years for *public services*) that precede the measurement of the individual-level dependent variables.

We also include potential confounders as control variables in the analysis. At the context level, we include the impact of the district-level share of foreigners and the economic situation. We measure the latter by contextual unemployment. As a robustness test, we then include the availability of services, the effect of which has been shown in the Dutch context (Harteveld, Van Der Brug, De Lange, & Van Der Meer, 2022). Previous research has also shown that the influence of the demographic context can be affected by the evaluation of the economic situation and by attitudes towards immigration (Krastev & Holmes, 2019; Salomo, 2019). Therefore, we control for the influence of these variables as well.

However, the model could be extended to include other mediation paths; for example, the influence of demographic context is likely mediated by other factors such as subjective assessment of the economic situation, attitudes towards immigration and so forth. These paths were not included in the model. However, since our attitudinal controls (*satisfaction with economy, immigration attitude, etc.*) are observed variables, the addition of the aforementioned pathways would not alter the estimated effect of the main tested mechanism.

All statistical analyses were conducted using Stata/BE (StataCorp, 2023). Stata’s *gsem* command uses the maximum number of non-missing observations for different equations within the model; the total number of observations employed in the estimation was 5874. The equation with the lowest number of observations (2,659) was that explaining party preference. The chief reason is that many participants responded that they would not vote in an election, resulting in missing observations in the party preference variable.

6. Empirical analysis

Before presenting the SEM model itself, we show in the following subsection how the above demographic indicators evolved in each district, that is, how some districts systematically shrank and others grew demographically. This subsection documents the magnitude of regionally determined demographic shifts.

6.1. Demographic decline in Czech districts

The maps in Fig. 2 contain two demographic indicators that describe demographic changes over a 10-year period: total population change in the districts and then average migration to/from the respective regions. The first two maps indicate that the districts near the two largest cities, Prague and Brno, have grown rather significantly in terms of demographics. Some districts have grown by as much as 30% in 10 years. The large cities of Prague and Brno have grown relatively less, presumably because of high housing prices and housing costs.

Contrariwise, demographic decline is especially visible in the peripheral border areas of the Czech Republic. These are regions that have been affected for a long time by structural problems, including, amongst other things, deindustrialization and reduced living standards (Bernard, Šimon, 2017). Population decline here has been substantial but remained at around 10% over the 10-year period.

⁴ Due to data availability, a longer period could not be used.

Fig. 1. Overview of the SEM model. Rectangles represent observed variables, double ovals represent district-level random effects, and single ovals represent (individual-level) latent variables; individual-level random effects are not shown for simplicity. The light blue shape identifies the measurement model for the latent social capital. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. Development of contextual variables in the Czech Republic, 2008–2017.

Given that demographic changes are rather gradual and long-term, the magnitude of these changes can be seen as a truly significant shift. The maps below also indicate that districts hit by economic problems (or characterized by a greater share of foreigners) do not overlap with demographic change; rather, these seem to have distinct dynamics.

Although it is not the purpose here to examine in detail the reasons

for these regional changes, it is important to note that regionally, changes in the demographic structure of the population have occurred in the CEE region also during periods of economic growth. Thus, the recent significant demographic change at the regional level is not only due to deindustrialization (which has been taking place since the early 1990s), but other factors have played a role. In this sense, attention is often

drawn to the role of EU cohesion policies, which, by investing in specific regions—mostly urban regions where universities and younger educated populations are located—increase regional disparities by supplying incentives to residents to change residence in favour of economically growing regions (Rehák et al., 2019). While this has brought economic development, at least to some regions, it has also fuelled population disparities between regions.

In the empirical analysis itself, these demographic indicators stood out as key variables. Thus, we worked with the variables that expressed change over the last 10 years, the assumption being that this change can permeate people's perceptions and influence other attitudes and/or behaviours.

6.2. Analysis of the full multilevel dataset

Table 1 presents the number of observations, descriptive statistics and pairwise correlations of all numeric variables. Before we estimated the full multilevel SEM model, we started with a small part of the model that only included the measurement equations of the latent *social capital* (the *measurement model*; see Fig. 1). The reason was that this part of the model is conceptually much more straightforward, and it allowed us to verify that *social capital* is measured correctly in the full model. In particular, the measurement model is a single-level model with dependent variables that can be approximated as continuous. In other words, it is a standard linear SEM model, which is easy to estimate and allows for the calculation of standard goodness-of-fit indices.

Running the measurement model with all measurement variables (*social trust*, *social networks*, *political discussion*, *donations/fundraising* and *social participation*) yielded results that were mildly underwhelming: some of the goodness-of-fit indices (RMSEA = 0.044, CFI = 0.874, TLI = 0.748, SRMR = 0.025) fell short of the recommended acceptance thresholds (Hu & Bentler, 1999), and the factor loading on the *social networks* variable was very low. Dropping this variable from the measurement model dramatically improved the fit (RMSEA = 0.009, CFI = 0.997, TLI = 0.992, SRMR = 0.007) and ensured all factor loadings were above 0.30. Therefore, we excluded *social networks* from further analyses.

Fig. 3 presents the main portion of the entire multilevel SEM model; complete results are available in Table 2. Regarding the effect of context, the results show that demographic context had a significant effect on social capital. Specifically, demographic decline was associated with lower levels of social capital.

Notably, demographic change had the strongest (and the only significant) effect on social capital among all contextual variables. In Fig. 4, Panel A facilitates a comparison of the effect sizes of the contextual variables by comparing the estimated change in *social capital* as each contextual variable alone moves from the lowest to the highest observed value (effectively comparing, e.g., typical differences in *social capital* in the district with the largest population decline to the district with the largest population growth, the net of the differences being due to the remaining contextual variables). Furthermore, the effect of *social capital* on choosing to support either SPD or ANO was statistically significant. However, the effect of social capital on SPD support is substantially stronger than in the case of ANO (SPD support: $\beta = 0.966$; ANO support: $\beta = 0.372$), and the difference is statistically significant ($p = 0.04$). This is to be expected as the link between populism and social capital is primarily due to the existence of exclusionary attitudes and negative evaluations of outgroups. It is logical that this effect is stronger for the radical nativist SPD than the more moderate ANO party. Fig. 4, Panel B compares the marginal effects of *social capital* on the probability of preferring SPD and ANO. As the standard deviation of *social capital* has been normalized to unity, the plot shows the impact of increasing *social capital* by one standard deviation.

Fig. 4, Panel C shows the estimated effect size along the entire path (*contextual variable* → *social capital* → *party preference*), in other words, the indirect effect of contextual variables on populist party preference

mediated via an individual's social capital (effectively, Panel C combines the results presented in panels A and B; the standard errors for the effect size have been obtained via the delta method). The results show that the difference between the least and most demographically prosperous districts might induce a change in social capital that will translate to a shift in SPD (ANO) support by approx. 2.6 pp (5.7 pp) from the current sample value of 5.27% (31.58%).

The estimated SEM model also included sociodemographic and attitudinal variables. These variables showed effects in the expected direction. SPD was more likely to be supported by people with negative attitudes towards migration, people dissatisfied with the economic situation, men rather than women and relatively younger people. In the case of ANO, its support was associated with an anti-immigration stance. This party was more likely to be supported by older people, those who had some experience with unemployment and those who were on the political right (based on subjective positioning).

6.3. Robustness checks

As mentioned in the methodology section, we check the robustness of our results by considering alternative contextual variables. The first check consisted in replacing *demographic change* (the overall population change over the 10-year period) with *net migration* (the average migration rate over the same timeframe). Fig. 5 in the Appendix presents key results for the latter; it can be noted that these results are almost identical to those presented in Fig. 4, showing robustness to different variations in the measurement of demographic trends.

The second robustness check included a variable measuring the availability of services in the region. This variable measured the change in the number of services in a given region over a 10-year period. This specification stems from the finding that demographic decline can manifest itself in the economic dimension, not only necessarily in terms of increased unemployment but also in terms of decreasing availability of services. Therefore, we also tested a model in which we used *public services*, a variable measuring the availability of services, instead of *unemployment rate*. The estimated effects along the path “*contextual variables* → *social capital* → *party preference*” are presented in Fig. 6 in the Appendix. Again, the results were qualitatively very similar to our main model (cf. Fig. 4). The *public services* variable did not seem to have a sizeable impact on *social capital*, and its inclusion did not compromise our earlier finding about the effect of *demographic change*. (In fact, in this alternative model specification, the effect of demographic change was even stronger and more statistically significant.)

Additionally, we also performed a robustness check related to the way the respondent's left-right position is measured. Since the ANO 2011 party is sometimes considered to be centrist-populist, we replaced the original numeric *left-right position* variable with a categorical variable with three levels (1–4 = left, 5–7 = centre, 8–11 = right) to distinguish the centre values.⁵ Regardless of this change, the results were very close to the original model. Notably, the estimated effect of *demographic change* was almost identical (see Fig. 7 in the Appendix).

Overall, the results of the SEM model show that a context characterized by long-term population decline and population outmigration is associated with lower levels of social capital. The latter is then associated with the choice of both the radical populist SPD and the more moderate populist ANO party.

6.4. Data constraints and limitations

An important feature of our dataset is the substantial proportion of missing values for some respondent-level characteristics. Non-response rates for attitudinal controls and social capital measures are approximately 35% (Table 1). To evaluate whether missing values might have

⁵ We thank an anonymous reviewer for suggesting this.

Table 1
Descriptive statistics and pairwise correlations of numeric variables.

	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.	10.	11.
<i>Party preference</i>																
1. SPD	3189	0.05	0.22	0	1	1.00										
2. ANO	3189	0.31	0.46	0	1	-0.16	1.00									
<i>Demographic controls</i>																
3. Female	7216	0.53	0.50	0	1	-0.02	-0.00	1.00								
4. Unemployed	4485	0.02	0.15	0	1	0.05	-0.01	-0.01	1.00							
<i>Attitudinal controls</i>																
5. Immigration attitude	4419	3.48	2.65	0	10	-0.12*	-0.11*	-0.04*	-0.02	1.00						
6. Satisf. with economy	4457	5.32	2.17	0	10	-0.13*	0.02	-0.14*	-0.05*	0.24*	1.00					
7. Left–right position	4133	5.44	2.35	0	10	-0.01	-0.02	0.02	-0.01	0.17*	0.15*	1.00				
8. Political interest	4488	2.53	0.93	1	4	-0.00	-0.01	0.21*	0.02	-0.06*	-0.13*	-0.02	1.00			
<i>Social capital measures</i>																
9. Social trust	5489	4.38	2.38	0	10	-0.09*	-0.02	-0.03	-0.02	0.19*	0.21*	0.07*	-0.09*	1.00		
10. Social networks	4488	4.15	1.08	1	6	-0.00	-0.01	0.06*	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.05*	-0.05*	0.02	1.00	
11. Political discussions	4486	2.47	0.93	1	4	0.00	-0.01	-0.21*	-0.02	0.06*	0.13*	0.02	-1.00	0.09*	0.05*	1.00
12. Donations/fundraising	5381	0.06	0.24	0	1	-0.03	-0.07*	-0.02	-0.03	0.14*	0.10*	0.06*	-0.12*	0.09*	-0.02	0.12*
13. Social participation	4489	1.72	0.53	1	6	-0.04	-0.04	0.05*	0.00	0.16*	0.13*	0.17*	-0.12*	0.12*	0.13*	0.12*
<i>Contextual variables</i>																
14. Demographic change	7216	0.80	4.91	-9.27	30.05	0.01	-0.11*	-0.00	-0.01	0.06*	0.04*	0.07*	-0.05*	0.07*	0.00	0.05*
15. Unemployment rate	7216	1.29	0.38	0.29	2.10	0.00	-0.10	0.00	0.05*	-0.08*	-0.03	-0.07*	0.05*	-0.05*	0.07*	-0.05*
16. Foreigners	7216	1.20	0.73	-0.02	2.71	-0.01	-0.07*	0.01	-0.00	0.12*	0.06*	0.10*	-0.08*	0.05*	-0.05*	0.08*
17. Net migration	7216	1.57	4.41	-6.08	26.61	0.01	-0.11*	-0.00	-0.01	0.07*	0.04*	0.08*	-0.05*	0.07*	-0.01	0.05*
18. Public services	7216	0.57	0.07	0.40	0.75	0.02	0.06*	-0.00	-0.03	-0.05*	-0.03	-0.05*	0.03	-0.01	-0.01	-0.03
							12.	13.	14.	15.	16.	17.	18.			
12. Donations/fundraising		1.00														
13. Social participation		0.10*			1.00											
<i>Contextual variables</i>																
14. Demographic change		0.03			0.10*			1.00								
15. Unemployment rate		-0.04*			-0.10*			-0.53*		1.00						
16. Foreigners		0.03			0.12*			0.39*		-0.38*		1.00				
17. Net migration		0.04*			0.12*			0.97*		-0.55*		0.51*		1.00		
18. Public services		-0.04*			-0.10			-0.42*		0.14*		-0.39*		-0.47		1.00

Notes: (i) Pairwise deletion of missing values applied in the calculations. (ii) * $p < 0.01$.

Fig. 3. Key findings of the SEM analysis. The figure presents statistically significant coefficients of the SEM model. Random effects, ordinal explanatory variables and measurement variables of *social capital* were all excluded from the figure for brevity. The variance of *social capital* has been standardized to 1 in the estimation process; the remaining variables and coefficients have not been standardized.

Table 2
Results of the SEM analysis.

Outcome:	Social capital		SPD preference		ANO preference	
	Coefficient	Standard error	Coefficient	Standard error	Coefficient	Standard error
Social capital			-0.966**	(0.294)	-0.372**	(0.124)
<i>Contextual variables</i>						
Demographic change (%)	0.0190*	(0.00854)	0.0385	(0.0253)	-0.0236	(0.0137)
Unemployment rate (log)	-0.145	(0.112)	0.0878	(0.371)	0.241	(0.161)
Foreigners (log)	0.0756	(0.0606)	0.0315	(0.198)	-0.0333	(0.0831)
<i>Demographic controls</i>						
Female			-0.451*	(0.206)	-0.0110	(0.0973)
Unemployed			0.621	(0.576)	-0.0287	(0.368)
Age						
• 15–19			0.235	(1.206)	-1.031	(1.084)
• 20–29			0.231	(0.419)	-0.314	(0.293)
• 30–44			ref.		ref.	
• 45–59			-0.338	(0.258)	0.407**	(0.140)
• 60+			-0.635*	(0.275)	0.972***	(0.135)
Education						
• None or elementary			-0.919	(0.587)	-0.0290	(0.223)
• Lower secondary			0.0147	(0.235)	0.207	(0.112)
• Upper secondary			ref.		ref.	
• Tertiary			-0.483	(0.265)	-0.435***	(0.120)
Household income						
• Low			-0.112	(0.422)	-0.443*	(0.199)
• Low medium			-0.307	(0.270)	-0.167	(0.116)
• Medium			ref.		ref.	
• High medium			-0.140	(0.255)	-0.00646	(0.125)
• High			0.223	(0.607)	-0.631	(0.402)
<i>Attitudinal controls</i>						
Immigration attitude			-0.225***	(0.0448)	-0.0710***	(0.0187)
Satisfaction with economy			-0.186***	(0.0461)	0.0312	(0.0231)
Left-right position			0.0444	(0.0422)	0.0507**	(0.0195)
Political interest			-0.296*	(0.146)	-0.0362	(0.0661)
<i>District random effect</i>			1	(restricted)	0.351	(0.226)
<i>Constant</i>			-0.112	(0.741)	-1.490***	(0.355)

Notes: (i) Standard errors in parentheses. (ii) For brevity, measurement equations for the latent variable social capital are not displayed; all loadings on *social capital* were positive and statistically significant in the measurement model (Fig. 3). (iii) * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Fig. 4. Marginal effects along the path “contextual variables → social capital → party preference”. In panels A and C, the points indicate the effect of varying the contextual variable from its sample minimum to its sample maximum, i.e., by changing its value by the entire sample range (this amounts to comparing the districts with the lowest and the highest value); panel B shows the effect of a unit increase in social capital (this corresponds to an increase by one standard deviation, as the variance of social capital is standardized). In panels B and C, the outcome is the change in the predicted probability of SPD or ANO preference. The calculation of this change required the choice of a baseline probability of SPD and ANO preference; we opted for the corresponding proportion of supporters in the sample: 5.27% for SPD and 31.58% for ANO. Finally, panel C only shows the mediated (indirect) effect of the contextual variables on party preferences; the direct unmediated path (contextual variable → party preference) was not included in the calculation.

biased our results, we carefully analysed the non-response patterns.

First, we compared the proportions of respondents supporting SPD and ANO 2011 in our data to results reported by the leading Czech polling agency Median. Our data collection spanned July–October 2017, the five months preceding that year’s parliamentary election. During this period, Median’s electoral models estimated support for ANO 2011 at 25–27.5% and SPD at 4.5–9.5%. In our sample, SPD was the party of choice for 5.3% of respondents who reported a party preference, while 31.6% supported ANO 2011. These results closely align with Median’s findings, suggesting no substantial selection bias in terms of party preference.

Second, we ran a series of logistic regressions to assess whether non-response in attitudinal controls and social capital measures varied systematically by (i) party preference and (ii) demographic characteristics. The results, summarized in Fig. 8 in the Appendix, indicate that non-response in these variables is unrelated to party preference. However, we observed some significant – though not particularly strong – patterns with respect to demographic characteristics. Non-respondents were more likely to be male, under 30, have low education levels, or report high household incomes. Importantly, as all these demographic characteristics are included as control variables in our statistical models, the main results are unlikely to be compromised by this uneven non-response.

A second limitation concerns the delimitation of contextual units (districts), as discussed in Section 5.1. Future analyses could explore the use of more homogeneous contextual units, provided that relevant data sources can be found. Such refinements could reduce statistical noise and potentially yield clearer results.

Finally, our analysis focuses on the party preferences of respondents who indicated they would vote in a parliamentary election, leaving open questions about the preferences of those who would not vote. Similar mechanisms may be at play in this group, which warrants investigation in future research.

7. Discussion and conclusions

This empirical analysis examines how demographic decline affects support for populist parties, based on the case of the Czech Republic as a

representative of post-communist CEE countries.

In recent decades, these countries have experienced a very strong population decline manifested by outmigration, low levels of natural increase and overall population loss (Johnson et al., 2015; Dijkstra, 2017). Not only have regions/countries such as eastern Germany and the Baltic states experienced spatial polarization due to demographic decline, but the CEE region as a whole has also been subjected to strong depopulation pressures. We have drawn upon Krastev and Holmes (2019) hypothesis that these population pressures will result in populist sentiments and support for populist parties. Thus, we have put forward a hypothesis and examined the attitudinal variables through which the effect of demographic decline on support for Czech populist political parties flows.

The results of this study support the hypothesis that demographic decline leads to a weakening of social capital, which in turn can act as a source of voting for both a radical populist (SPD) and a more moderate populist (ANO) party.

The findings of this article put into context phenomena that used to be perceived separately. Demographic decline has been perceived as a common characteristic of many countries in the post-communist CEE region (Kühn, 2015). These countries have traditionally been characterized by the strong presence of populist and illiberal sentiments, including electorally successful populist parties (Santana et al., 2020; Stanley, 2017). Our analysis points to social capital as a mechanism linking these two elements.

The effects of demographic decline described here can be understood through the logic of grievance theory (Rydgren, 2007), as the consequences of macro-structural processes that lead to discontent at the individual level. Demographic factors are at work in the case of CEE countries because of the structural transformations of these societies over the last 30 years.

Our results suggest that demographic decline in post-communist CEE countries affects the choice of populist parties. However, these results may not be limited to this region alone, and the path from demographic decline to the breakdown of social capital to the election of populist parties can also exist in other regions—it is a general phenomenon. The association between demographic decline, declining social capital and the tendency to vote for radical nativist populist parties may also be

valid in WE and non-European contexts.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Tomáš Dvořák: Writing – original draft, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Jan Zouhar:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Data analysis, Data curation. **Jan Bíba:** Writing – original draft.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

APPENDIX

Fig. 5. Marginal effects along the path “contextual variables → social capital → party preference” in an alternative model specification that uses *net migration* instead of *demographic change*. See Fig. 4 for a detailed description of the content of individual panels.

Fig. 6. Marginal effects along the path “contextual variables → social capital → party preference” in an alternative model specification that uses *public services* instead of *unemployment rate*. See Fig. 4 for a detailed description of the content of individual panels.

Fig. 7. Marginal effects along the path “contextual variables → social capital → party preference” in an alternative model specification that measures the respondent’s left-right position using a categorical variable (left, centre, right) instead of the original numeric variable (11-point scale). See Fig. 4 for a detailed description of the content of individual panels.

Fig. 8. Results of logistic regressions exploring the pattern of missing values in attitudinal controls and social capital measures. For each of these variables, we created a binary indicator of a missing value and regressed it on (i) party preference and (ii) demographic characteristics. The plot shows the average marginal effects of individual explanatory variables, and their 95% confidence intervals (obtained by the Delta method).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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